

ANALYSIS OF BRAIDED TUBES SUBJECTED TO INTERNAL PRESSURE

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1. Introduction

The increase in the use of composite structures in high integrity applications has been driven by the excellent specific properties that are delivered by polymer matrix composites. Over the past five years the use of carbon fibre composites in the aerospace industry has received much media attention as the latest generations of passenger aircraft make the transition to composite structures.

Composite preforming through braiding produces composites with interlaced tow architectures. This can be beneficial in terms of damage tolerance but can also lead to reductions in the Ultimate Tensile Strength and Modulus of the composite material. In this work a Finite Element model of the braid Representative Volume Element (RVE) was constructed. The parameters of the unit cell were obtained by geometrical relationships and analysis of Computed Tomography data. The RVE was evaluated to determine the tensile strength and equivalent moduli of the braided composite. This was used in a macro-model of the composite tube to assess burst strength. The model was verified using data gained experimentally.

The prediction of modulus in textile composites has a strong foundation in methods related to composite laminate theory. Ishikawa and Chou's work produced the Mosaic [1] and Undulation [2] models for prediction of material constants in reinforced composites using textiles. The undulation model was further developed by Naik who produced a 2D model by considering a 3D unit cell [3]. This accounted for the different interlacement geometries in two directions of the unit cell. Similar studies

have been carried out specifically for braided reinforcement. Smith and Swanson [4] examined compression responses of braided composites and examined the effects of crimp angle on composite modulus. Naik developed a model capable of predicting the mechanical properties and test data trends for braid structures with different architectures [5].

Potluri and Manan presented an analysis of the geometry and the related mechanical properties of non-orthogonally interlaced structures [6]. A finite element model was constructed and simulated results were compared with experimental data. The limit strength of the RVE was also predicted using the finite element model.

In this work, braid reinforced composite tubes have been subjected to internal pressure loading. The behavior of the braid structure under such loading conditions has been examined. Similar work by Tsai examined the microstructure of braided composite tubes [7]. Laminate theory based analyses were performed, namely the mosaic and undulation models were found to give good predictions of composite elastic behavior. The current study aims to provide a Tomography driven finite element (FE) analysis of the braid RVE, to predict the failure stresses of the tubes and provide modulus data to be used in a macro-scale model.

2. Unit Cell Characterisation

In order to produce an accurate finite element representation of the braid unit cell, an analysis of the tow architecture in the braid is required.

Figure 1: Measurement of crimp angle in a textile composite

Figure 1 shows the interlacement of tows in textile reinforcement. The degree of deviation from the lamina centre line is measured by the crimp angle. The unit cell parameters were obtained using geometrical relations, these dimensions were verified using meso-scale tomography images of the braided architecture.

3. Finite Element Model

The finite element unit cell used in the current work was based on the work of Potluri and Manan [6]. A repeat unit was constructed from eight separate regions. The tows orientated in the positive angle are represented by one continuous tow and smaller tow segments. The tows orientated at the negative angle are similarly represented. Two resin pockets also exist and represent the resin rich regions that occur due to interlacement. Similar models were produced for braid angles of 20° and 65° to study the changes in modulus with changing braid angle and crimp angle. Figure 2 shows the constituent components of the unit cell. Images (a) and (d) represent resin pocket. Images (b) and (c) represent the interlacing tows of the braid at angles $\pm\theta$.

The unit cell was loaded in the longitudinal direction and appropriate constraints were applied to the faces of the model. The stresses and strains in the model were examined and used to calculate the material constants and ultimate strength of the braid. A macro scale model of the composite tube was constructed. The material properties obtained from the from

the unit cell model were used in the model to obtain predictions of the failure strength at burst. This was compared to the failure initiation stresses found in the interlaced composite model.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 2: FE representation of the braided unit cell.

4. Experimental

A 48-carrier braiding machine was used to manufacture 2x2 carbon fibre preforms with both circumferential and longitudinal reinforcement. A mandrel was used to form the composite reinforcement. The cylindrical part was then infused using epoxy resin. The reinforcement was placed into a rigid match

mould. A pressure pot injector was used to inject the resin at 0.5 bar.

The samples were produced using Toray T700-50C 12k carbon fibre tows and infused with Araldite LY564 resin and allowed to cure at room temperature. A post cure was performed at 80°C for four hours.

The tubes were loaded internally until burst failure occurred and the failure pressure was recorded.

5. Results

5.1 Unit Cell Analysis

Figure 3: Braided angle measurement from CT Data

The unit cell parameters were measured from CT images such as the one shown in Figure 3. The measured dimensions are shown in Table 1

Unit Cell Parameter	Braided Angle		
	20°	65°	80°
Thickness (mm)	0.4	0.6	0.6
Repeat Unit Length (mm)	2	5	7
Repeat Unit Width (mm)	7	4	2

Table 1: Unit Cell parameters

5.2 FE Modulus Predictions

The modulus in the E_{11} (circumferential direction) and E_{22} (longitudinal direction) were determined by averaging the stress and strain in modeled volume elements and are shown in Table 2.

Braided Angle	Crimp Angle	FEA E_{11} Modulus (GPa)	FEA E_{22} Modulus (GPa)
20°	7°	7.5	82.1
65°	16°	43.0	27.3
80°	18°	47.0	7.8

Table 2: Moduli of braided RVE models in E_{11} and E_{22}

The modulus of the three geometries were also predicted using Lehnitskii methodology [REF]. A comparison between the FE obtained moduli and analytically obtained moduli is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Comparison of E_{11} from FEA and Lehnitskii Predictions

Preliminary Strength Analysis

The strength of the braided structure has been computed using the finite element analysis. All burst pressure samples were found to fail in the hoop mode under internal pressure. The mean burst pressure of the samples was 1100 MPa.

As the failure mode was exclusively in the hoop direction, the strength of the circumferential layers has been explored. A macro-model of the tube was constructed to predict the stresses in the hoop layers of the tube at failure. The maximum stress in the hoop layer at the burst pressure was found to be 2338 MPa. This laminate stress was applied to the meso-scale RVE model. The maximum stress along the tow direction was found to be 3140 MPa. Given a 69% fibre volume fraction in the composite tows the fibre stress at failure in the braises tow has been predicted as 4550 MPa, which is 93% of the strength of carbon fibre.

6. Conclusions

The finite element RVE has been used to predict the modulus in the E_{11} and E_{22} directions of three representative unit cell models. The moduli obtained from the finite element models show good agreement with Lekhnitskii methodology predictions. The stress fields show an increased region of stress at the points of interlacement. This is associated with a reduction in strength of the braided composite. The model predicts stresses that are 30% higher than the applied RVE stress at the points of interlacement.

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8. References

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